

IPBES TCA Chapter 3. Identification of on-going initiatives with transformative potential and pitfalls / IPBES transformative change assessment (3.3)

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Description

The review corresponds to the IPBES transformative change assessment. The IPBES scoping document for the transformative change assessment describes that chapter 3 should address how transformative change occurs, focusing on those changes that can be intentionally promoted, accelerated, and scaled to realize a sustainable world where biodiversity can thrive. The chapter showcases a selection of representative historical examples and case studies of transformative change, highlighting both the possibilities and challenges of achieving a just and sustainable world. A database was developed with the overarching goal of collating studies, projects, ventures and initiatives (collectively referred to as "case studies") that illustrate key elements of transformative change, including challenges, views, structures, practices, strategies, and outcomes, as well as the roles of various actor groups. In this context, a selection of case studies and analysis of the case studies database from the assessment was conducted and is further described below. The case studies complement one another in understanding the transformative change process, showcasing different combinations of challenges, strategies, and actor constellations. As a result, they demonstrate the varied quality, direction, and breadth of transformative processes.

Process overview

Protocol

The case studies database (B) for the transformative change assessment was developed with the overarching goal to develop a database of studies, projects, ventures, initiatives, practices, technologies (collectively referred to as ‘examples’) that provide evidence on how transformative change occurs or can potentially happen and how existing challenges in this regard can be overcome, while providing relevant information for policymakers and all other stakeholders.

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** questionnaire (A)
- **Search languages:** English
- **Engine:** Google Forms
- **Sample extracted:** 407 case studies from 87 contributors¹
- **Treatment applied:**

Methodology for Figure 3.6:

The analysis shown in Figure 3.6 was based on the categorization of case studies according to several factors.

- **Timeframe for change (Panel A):** Data on the timeframes within which transformative outcomes were observed was gathered from the questionnaire responses. The questionnaire asked respondents to provide the start and end dates of the initiatives, as well as the observed timing for significant changes in the social, economic, or environmental dimensions. This information was then categorized into time intervals (e.g., within a decade or longer) to allow for a comparative analysis of the duration required to achieve positive outcomes.
- **Nature’s contributions to people outcomes (Panel B):** For the analysis of nature’s contributions to people, respondents were asked to identify which contributions or ecosystem services were positively (or negatively) affected by the initiative. These included aspects such as clean air, water, food provision, and cultural benefits. The responses were analyzed using predefined categories based on previous IPBES assessments, and the number of initiatives reporting positive or negative outcomes in each category was aggregated.
- **Socio-economic outcomes (Panel C):** The analysis of socio-economic outcomes was similarly based on questionnaire data, where respondents specified the types of socio-economic benefits observed (e.g., poverty reduction, improved health, or increased equity). These responses were also categorized, and the initiatives were grouped based on the socio-economic dimensions they addressed.

Methodology for Figure 3.7:

Figure 3.7 involved a network analysis of actor group collaborations. Another key feature of this analysis was the development of a composite index to measure the combined impact of the number of actor groups on both nature’s contributions to people and socioeconomic outcomes.

- A network analysis was conducted on the actors involved in ongoing initiatives with transformative potential. The lines represent the number of initiatives that two agents share, while the size of the circle indicates the number of initiatives in which each agent is involved. A division of communities was done using Louvain's algorithm. This algorithm groups the nodes to maximize a mathematical function called modularity. It considers several groups of nodes and selects the groups that maximize such function. For this purpose, the algorithm separates nodes that are highly connected to each other and have few connections to other groups. In addition, it takes into account the weights of the links when calculating the clusters. A mathematical

¹ See main data management report on the case study database for further details:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10260234>

description of the modularity function can be found at Blondel et al., 2008. Cases with questionable foundations, insufficient support, or that reflected the author's personal opinion on a global topic or issue were excluded.

- Composite indices for nature's contributions to people and socioeconomic impacts: Two separate composite indices were developed to measure the overall impact of the initiatives on nature's contributions to people and socioeconomic indicators: For each initiative, respondents indicated which nature's contribution to people or socio-economic indicators were positively impacted. These indicators were assigned numerical scores based on the magnitude and significance of the impacts reported. The scores across different indicators were aggregated to create a composite index representing the overall contribution of the initiative to nature's contributions to people or socio-economic outcomes, which enabled a unified measure to evaluate their outcomes across different case studies.
 - Correlation with actor group collaboration: The level of actor group collaboration was statistically correlated with the two composite indices for nature's contributions to people and socioeconomic outcomes. The analysis demonstrated a significant positive correlation ($p < 0.01$) between broader cross-community collaboration and higher composite index scores for both types of outcomes. This finding indicates that initiatives involving more diverse collaborations between actor groups tend to achieve more positive transformative outcomes in both domains.
- **Final sample:** 391 case studies.

The results from this analysis are presented in section 3.4.

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	1_IP- BES_TCA_3.3_07_2024_(A)	CSV	42 KB	List of questions from the case study database questionnaire
B	2_IP- BES_TCA_3.3_11_2024_(B)	CSV	1,8 KB	Full case study database